

Viruses and Bacteria

Spot the difference!

Viruses are not considered living organisms. They are usually smaller than $0.5\mu\text{m}$

They are not able to reproduce on their own and to do so need to infect a cell

They can be structurally very simple with or without a lipid envelope (comparable to a cell membrane). Can evolve very quickly and quickly adapt to new hosts

They may not survive long outside a host organism

They cause infections that must be treated with **anti-viral** drugs but may quickly become resistant to these drugs

Bacteria are living organisms made of a single cell. Their size usually ranges between $1-5\mu\text{m}$

They reproduce autonomously

They can have a wide host range

They may survive for a long time outside a host organism

They cause infections that must be treated with **antibiotics** but the overuse of these drugs is favouring the selection and diffusion of antibiotic resistant bacterial strains

The good news:

The best defence against pathogenic viruses and bacteria is the immune system as the activation of an effective immune response, by inhibiting the multiplication of the pathogens, prevents the onset of symptoms and the development of the diseases.

Vaccines “educate” the immune system teaching it to recognise pathogenic viruses and bacteria so that it can effectively prevent infections.